

D1.1 Comprehensive overview of the project

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Executive Summary

Steel4Fatigue project aims to investigate fatigue-optimised solutions for dynamic components in the automotive industry. It will achieve this by introducing new materials and technologies to reduce the weight of trucks and cars by 10%. These solutions will be based on specially developed materials with high fatigue performance (AHSS and spring steels), advanced computer modelling for accurate fatigue prediction, and innovative experimental methodologies to reduce testing time. The project will also focus on minimising environmental impact evaluated through life cycle assessment, reducing energy consumption and material usage through improved steelmaking processes, and enhancing fatigue performance to facilitate wider market adoption of *Steel4Fatigue* solutions. Attention will be given to steelmaking, including internal defects and scrap quality, as well as manufacturing processes like cold forming and mechanical shearing to better understand their impact on the fatigue performance of cyclic-loaded components. To achieve these goals, the project will develop methods for evaluating these effects and improving the fatigue design of selected demonstrators. It will also explore microstructures for optimal fatigue performance. Two industrial demonstrators will be defined to validate the proposed solutions. The project's contributions include reducing lead times to market through advanced fatigue testing methodologies and models. The outcomes will provide materials, modelling, and experimental tools for designing fatigue-resistant parts across multiple sectors. Practical guidelines will be established for factors such as proposed microstructures, advanced testing, modelling approaches, and the influence of manufacturing and steelmaking processes on part performance.

The present deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the *Steel4Fatigue* project.

The document describes in detail the state of the art of the thick 1st generation Advanced High Strength Steels (AHSS) and spring steels. A literature review on the influence of microstructural constituents on the mechanical performance of these steels is presented. The review covers a broad range of critical in-use properties such as formability, fatigue, notch sensitivity and fracture toughness.

The report identifies the knowledge gaps and main challenges found in the implementation of these new thick AHSS grades and outlines the novel experimental and modelling approaches of *Steel4Fatigue* to overcome them.

Finally, the expected outcomes of the project and how are they aligned with the proposed work plan are described.

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Terminology and acronyms

A	Austenite
AHSS	Advanced High Strength Steels
ART	Austenite Reverted Transformation
BCC	Body Centred Cubic
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
BiW	Body-in-White
CA	Cellular Automata
CFRP	Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer
CM	Martensite Carbon content
CP	Complex Phase
CPM	Crystal Plasticity Modelling
CRI	Critical Resistance Index
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DENT	Double Edge Notched Tension
DIC	Digital Image Correlation
DNSH	Do Not Significant Harm
DP	Dual Phase
EO	Expected Outcomes
EFW	Essential Work of Fracture
F	Ferrite
FCC	Face Centred Cubic
FEM	Finite Element Modelling
FLC	Forming Limit Curve
FLD	Forming Limit Diagram
GHG	Greenhouse gas emissions
GND	Geometrically Necessary Dislocations
HDV	Heavy Duty Vehicles
HR	Hot Rolled
HR-EBSD	High Resolution Electron Backscattered Diffraction
HSS	High Strength Steels
IR	Infrared
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LOM	Light Optical Microscopy

M	Martensite
N	Number of cycles to failure
PFM	Phase Field Models
R	Stress Ratio
S	Stress
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SENB	Single Edge Notched Bending
SF	Ferrite grain size
SIF	Stress Intensity Factor
SM	Martensite Grain Size
TE	Total Elongation
TO	Technical Objectives
TRIP	Transformation-Induced Plasticity
TTT	Time- Temperature- Transformation
UTS	Ultimate Tensile Strength
VM	Martensite Volume Fraction
XFEM	Extended FEM
ZEV	Zero Emission Vehicles

1. Introduction

The main aim of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive overview of the *Steel4Fatigue* project. This overview includes an updated description of the state-of-the-art on 1st generation Advanced High Strength Steels (AHSS) and spring steels for automotive applications. Different aspects like microstructural characteristics, mechanical properties, formability, fatigue and fracture are considered.

The main challenges related to the widespread implementation of these thick 1st generation AHSSs in the automotive industry and how the *Steel4Fatigue* approach addresses them are discussed. The main objectives and expected outcomes of the *Steel4Fatigue* project are described and a detailed description of the multidisciplinary strategy followed to reach such objectives is provided.

2. State of the art

2.1 Advanced High Strength Steels

Advanced High-Strength Steels (AHSS) are a class of steel with high strength and ductility (yield strength > 300 MPa and tensile strength > 600 MPa), making them ideal for critical structural applications, particularly in the automotive industry. These materials are crucial for achieving lightweight designs while maintaining vehicle safety, crashworthiness, and durability standards in response to an increasing need for higher vehicle performance and fuel economy [1-3]. While the strengthening mechanisms such as solid solution strengthening, grain refinement, and precipitation strengthening typically result in a decrease in formability in conventional high strength steels (HSS) mainly containing predominantly ferrite microstructure, AHSS steels provide a combination of high ductility and strength due to a multi-phase complex microstructure [4].

Figure 1 compares conventional and advanced high-strength steels in terms of the combination of tensile strength and ductility, emphasising the high toughness, high ductility, and high strength of the AHSS steels [5].

Figure 1. Tensile strength versus elongation for conventional HSS and advanced HSS steels [5].

AHSS can be divided into several classes based on their tensile strength or microstructure. The 1st generation of AHSS steels can be categorised into four distinct classes as dual phase (DP), transformation-induced plasticity (TRIP) steels, complex-phase (CP) steels, and martensitic steels based on the microstructure, toughness, hardness, and hardening mechanisms [6].

2.1.1 Dual-Phase (DP) Steels

As the first generation of AHSS steels, DP steels are manufactured involving specific phase transformations to reach a ferritic-martensitic microstructure with 15 to 25 % volume fraction of martensite islands embedded in a ferrite matrix [7, 8]. A typical DP steel microstructure is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Scanning electron microscopy image of a typical microstructure of the DP steel containing ferrite matrix and martensitic islands [9].

The phase transformation path to obtain this microstructure is indicated in Figure 3. There are two heat-treatment paths to produce DP steels. The material is initially held in

an austenite-ferrite zone, followed by quenching and then holding at temperatures just below the martensite start point, which allows the austenite phase to convert into martensite. Alternatively, the quenching rate from the fully austenitic state can be adjusted so that most of the undercooled austenite transforms into ferrite, while the remaining portion turns into martensite [10].

Figure 3. The TTT (Time-Temperature-Transformation) plot shows the heat-treatment procedure to obtain a ferritic-martensitic microstructure in DP steels where A, F, and M represent Austenite, Ferrite, and Martensite respectively [10].

This dual-phase microstructure of DP steels results in unique mechanical properties such as a high balance of strength and ductility with a tensile strength varying from 450 to 1200 MPa [11]. Several parameters such as the chemical composition, initial microstructure, and the heat-treatment procedure can affect the DP steel final microstructure in terms of generation of different phases, rather than ferrite and martensite, martensite volume fraction (VM), martensite grain size (SM), martensite carbon content (CM), martensite/ferrite morphology, ferrite grain size (SF), ferrite texture, density of transformation-induced geometrically necessary dislocations (GNDs), micro- and mesoscale segregation, and the chemical decoration state of the heterointerfaces [12-15]. All these changes can result in altered mechanical properties of DP steels. Accordingly, to obtain the desired DP steel with the required microstructural and mechanical properties, a careful composition selection and heat-treatment design are required.

2.1.2 Transformation-Induced Plasticity (TRIP) Steels

TRIP steels use retained austenite that transforms into martensite under deformation, providing excellent strength and ductility. Their complex microstructure, including ferrite, bainite, and retained austenite allows these steels to absorb energy during deformation and provides more than 1000 MPa of UTS and ductility of 20 to 30% or more, making them highly effective in crash-resistant applications [16, 17]. To better understand the TRIP steels, it is mandatory to know the TRIP effect. The Transformation-Induced Plasticity (TRIP) effect in steels significantly improves both strength and ductility by promoting the transformation of austenite into martensite during plastic deformation. This transformation, occurring near or at room temperature, produces a high-carbon

martensite phase, which boosts the strain-hardening rate and strengthens the material, as seen in Figure 4. The gradual conversion of austenite into martensite during deformation causes irregularities and results in high strain-hardening, delaying necking and allowing the material to maintain or even increase its ductility despite higher strength.

Figure 4. Flow curves of a meta-stable austenitic stainless showing the strain-induced α' martensite formation [18].

Figure 5 illustrates an example of TRIP steel microstructure produced by austenite reverted transformation (ART) heat-treatment procedure. As can be inferred from the figure, different austenitisation temperatures can change the final microstructure. In general, the final microstructure of the steel can vary based on chemical composition and the heat-treatment procedure which defines the final volume fraction of each phase and the mechanical properties. This fact highlights the importance of a careful production process design of TRIP steels to achieve the intended properties [19].

Figure 5. SEM micrographs of ART TRIP steels for 12 h at 650 °C after austenitisation at (a) 800 °C, (b) 850 °C, (c) 900 °C with 1 h. (A: austenite, F: ferrite, M: martensite) [19].

2.1.3 Complex-Phase (CP) Steels

The microstructure of complex phase (CP) steels is composed of ferrite, martensite, and bainite as can be detected in Figure 6. Bainite itself is a mixed structure that contains lath-like bainitic ferrite, which is accompanied by small martensitic islands at the microscale and precipitates, such as carbides or carbonitrides, at the nanoscale. The formation of these precipitates consumes carbon, which results in the depletion of carbon in the surrounding matrix. Because of this carbon depletion, there is insufficient carbon available to stabilise any remaining austenite during cooling, preventing the formation of retained austenite in CP steels. The presence of the bainite which smoothens the hardness transition between the softer phase such as ferrite and the harder phase such as martensite and the absence of retained austenite are distinguishing factors in the microstructure of CP steels, contributing to their unique combination of high strength, ductility, fracture toughness and hole expansion properties compared to other AHSS steels [20-22].

Figure 6. A typical microstructure of a CP steel mainly consists of a mixture of bainite, martensite, and ferrite phases [20].

This unique microstructure gives CP steels excellent mechanical properties, such as high tensile strength of at least 800 MPa, enhanced toughness, and good formability, making them proper choices for wide use in structural parts of automobile chassis, such as torsion beams and suspension arms, etc [21]. However, it is challenging to ensure the proper final microstructure in order to achieve the desired in-service mechanical properties due to the very complex microstructure in these types of steels which highlights the importance of a very careful composition control and production process design [23]. To design the heat treatment process, several parameters such as austenitisation temperature, cooling rate in quenching temperature, isothermal holding condition to produce desired bainite phase, and tempering temperature to generate tempered martensite should be controlled to ensure the balance between strength and ductility [24].

2.1.4 Martensitic Steels

Martensitic steels are another type of AHSS steels, composed almost entirely of martensite, resulting in ultra-high strength. However, they are less formable compared to DP or TRIP steels, so they are used primarily in applications requiring high strength over ductility, such as structural reinforcements in vehicles. The microstructure

predominantly consists of lath martensite, as shown in Figure 7. Martensitic sheet steels offer some of the highest strength levels, with ultimate tensile strengths reaching up to 1500 MPa. To enhance ductility, they often undergo post-quench tempering, which improves formability even at very high strength. Carbon is added to increase hardenability and strengthen the martensite phase. Additionally, alloying elements such as manganese, silicon, chromium, molybdenum, boron, vanadium, and nickel are used in various combinations to further enhance hardenability and optimise mechanical properties [20].

Figure 7. Optical microscopy of the microstructure of martensitic steel, containing mostly martensitic laths [20].

2.2 Mechanical tests

Mechanical testing of AHSS is critical for evaluating their performance under various conditions, especially when designing automotive and structural components. Several standard mechanical tests are commonly used to assess the properties of AHSS materials, focusing on aspects like strength, formability, and durability. These tests are essential to ensure that AHSS meets the required specifications for applications in high-stress environments [25]. Fatigue tests are addressed in section 2.4 while fracture toughness tests are addressed in section 6.2.3.

2.2.1 Tensile Test

The main motivation for developing all types of AHSS is to have a combination of strength and ductility in terms of yield and ultimate tensile strength and elongation to fracture. As a result, the tensile test is the most basic and widely used method to evaluate the quality of AHSS. It helps in understanding the steel's ability to withstand pulling forces and its deformation characteristics. For AHSS, tensile tests can be used to evaluate the steel's ductility and strength-to-weight ratio. Figure 8 presents a typical stress-strain curve obtained from the tensile testing. Tensile properties and strain to fracture can be representatives of the strength and ductility of different AHSS types, highlighting the higher strength and lower ductility of the martensitic AHSS specimen compared to CP and DP ones [26].

Figure 8. Stress-strain curves obtained by the low strain rate tensile tests for CP, DP, and martensitic AHSS specimens [26].

2.2.2 Forming Limit Diagram (FLD)

The Forming Limit Diagram is used to assess the formability of AHSS, particularly in sheet metal applications. It determines the strain limits for various materials during forming operations like stamping. The FLD is crucial for understanding how AHSS will perform under real-world manufacturing conditions, including deep drawing, stamping, and bending these tests are necessary in the automobile industry as AHSS parts need to have acceptable formability in order to produce automobile parts like chassis components and wheels [27]. Figure 9 shows a typical FLD with five main strain states in sheet-forming processes. FLD plot illustrates the area between the major and minor true strains under different strain paths. This curve is generated by applying various failure criteria, most of which are based on strain localisation or crack initiation. By establishing an FLC using these failure criteria, it becomes possible to identify safe regions where the material can deform without failure, as well as regions where failure is likely to occur [28].

Figure 9. Typical FLD with five main strain states in sheet-forming processes [27].

2.3 Microstructural modelling of AHSS

Microstructural modelling of AHSS plays a critical role in predicting the material's behaviour under various mechanical and thermal conditions. To optimise the performance of AHSS and spring steels and guide the design of new steel grades, researchers employ various microstructural modelling techniques that simulate the material's behaviour at the micro and macroscopic levels. Exceptional mechanical properties of the AHSS are highly related to the presence of different phases in a complex microstructure. As a result, careful and accurate heat treatments and prediction of generated phases and their morphology are required to achieve intended properties such as strength and ductility. Phase field models (PFM) are widely used to simulate the evolution of microstructures in AHSS. These models help in understanding the transformation of different phases during processing, such as the formation of martensite in DP steels or the transformation of retained austenite in TRIP steels under stress and nucleation mechanisms of different phases. By using these models, researchers can predict how microstructures will evolve during heat treatment and deformation processes, aiding in the optimisation of the processing parameters to achieve desired material properties [30-32]. Figure 10 illustrates an example of a 2D PFM simulation of microstructure evolution and the formation of ferrite and austenite from a constant austenite grain size and different cooling rates taking into account the effect of cooling rate in determining the volume percentage, morphology, and location of phases in the microstructure [30].

Figure 10. 2D PFM simulation of microstructure evolution and the formation of ferrite and austenite from a constant austenite grain size and different cooling rates with ferrite in white, austenite in orange, and interfaces in blue [30].

Another popular way to predict the behaviour of the AHSS is the Crystal Plasticity Modelling (CPM) method. This modelling method is used to simulate the behaviour of individual grains and predict the overall mechanical response of AHSS. These models take into account the crystallographic orientation of grains, which is particularly important for materials like TWIP steels, where the deformation is highly dependent on the

activation of specific slip systems within the crystal lattice. Crystal plasticity models are essential for understanding the anisotropic behaviour of AHSS during forming processes. By modelling individual grains and their crystallographic orientation, CPM helps in understanding how different phases, such as ferrite and martensite, interact during deformation. It predicts key phenomena like slip, twinning, strain hardening, and phase transformations. CPM is particularly useful in studying formability, fatigue, and fracture behaviour in AHSS, optimising their performance for applications like automotive components [33-35].

Cellular automata (CA) models are another approach used for simulating the microstructure evolution of AHSS. These models are particularly useful for predicting the grain growth, phase transformation kinetics, and texture development that occur during heat treatment or deformation processes. By simulating the dynamic processes at the microscale, CA models provide valuable insights into how to control the microstructure to enhance mechanical properties like strength, ductility, and toughness. CA model is a grid-based computational method where each cell has a finite number of states, and its state evolves based on a set of user-defined transition rules. The state change in each cell depends on the state of neighbouring cells and its own state from the previous time step [36]. A key advantage of CA is its ability to handle large computational domains, leading to more accurate simulations. This method has been used in microstructural evolution simulations, including processes like re-austenitisation [37], recrystallisation [38], and austenite-to-ferrite transformation [39]. Figure 11 shows an example of how CA simulation can study microstructure behaviour in the intermediate stages of austenitisation [36].

Figure 11. Microstructural evolution during austenitisation of a DP steel: (a) input microstructure and phase transformation progress at (a-e) different temperatures from 740 to 860 °C [36].

To perform several types of modelling from microstructural evolutions to mechanical properties under different service conditions, Finite Element Modelling (FEM) is extensively employed. FEM provides opportunities to simulate the mechanical behaviour of AHSS materials during forming operations by integrating material models that describe plasticity and phase transformation behaviours. FEM can predict the material's deformation, strain distribution, and stress state in real-world. This approach helps manufacturers optimise processes to minimise defects like cracking and wrinkling. Several works can be presented as examples of employing FEM simulation to study AHSS microstructural and mechanical properties evolution during different forming methods or loading conditions. Sartkulvanich [40] used FEM to simulate edge cracking in the flanging of AHSS DP590 which can be a challenge as it can occur at lower strains than those predicted by the forming limit curves (FLC) and it is influenced significantly by the sheared or blanked edge quality. FEM was employed to investigate the edge integrity under varying punch/die clearances during blanking. The simulation of hole expansion was conducted to explore the influence of the sheared edge on material stretchability. This approach enabled an assessment of how metal flow, strain distribution, and stress development during blanking impact overall part quality and the potential for edge cracking in stretch flanging processes. Experimental validation showed the simulation results have less than 6% error which can significantly reduce the time and cost compared to conventional trial and error experiments. Sun [41] used FEM to study the roll forming in fabricating AHSS. Figure 12 shows the simulation sequence and how FEM models can replicate the real forming process and help reduce the experimental tests.

Figure 12. The simulation sequences: (a) the workpiece engaged with the tools; (b) forming the workpiece; (c) the tools move away from the workpiece, (d) the released stress-strain by springback [41].

Sajek [42] utilised FEM modelling to investigate the phase transformation of welded AHSS in the heat-affected zone by simulating the cooling rates concerning TTT diagrams of the corresponding steel. Figure 13 represents and compares the simulation and experimental obtained data of the fusion zone and heated area to prove the abilities of the FEM to replicate the real process. Simulations enabled the characterisation of the thermal cycle at any specific point in the weld, using various welded joint geometries and a broad spectrum of simple to complex heat sources. As a result, the entire thermal

history of the joint area can be thoroughly examined, allowing for a precise interpretation of the structural phenomena occurring within the weld in AHSS.

Figure 13. Comparison of fusion determined by means of FEM with the actual fusion [42].

These examples among numerous others once again prove the vast abilities of the FEM simulation methods to be used in order to better understand and improve the quality and application of AHSS.

2.4 Fatigue characterisation and modelling

Material defects and fatigue modelling are critical in understanding the durability and reliability of AHSS and spring steels, especially when these materials are used in structural applications like automotive components. These steels are designed for high strength, but they also need to maintain performance under cyclic loading, which often leads to fatigue failures. Inclusions (non-metallic particles such as oxides, sulphides, or silicates) and voids can be generated during the production steps and severely affect the mechanical properties of AHSS. These defects can act as stress concentrators, leading to early failure under stress. Inclusions may promote crack initiation, while voids can cause the material to lose its ability to bear load. The presence of defects at grain boundaries, particularly in high-strength steels like martensitic and dual-phase steels, can lead to intergranular fracture. These defects are often associated with poor heat treatment or manufacturing inconsistencies, which may impact the steel's fatigue performance. Surface or edge cracks are other types of defects that can promote early in-service or during-production failures by providing stress concentration zones and preferable sites for fatigue and fracture initiations. The size, density, location, and geometry of these defects determine the level of negative effects they provide to the AHSS application [43-45].

One of the main concerns about the presence of different defect types in AHSS and spring steels is how they can promote fatigue by reducing the resistance and providing the preferable initiation sites [45]. Fatigue is a critical consideration for AHSS and spring steels, especially in dynamic loading conditions such as those experienced in automotive components during everyday use (e.g., suspension systems, chassis components, etc.). Figure 14 shows a typical fatigue fracture in AHSS showing the crack initiation site from the surface and the burr from a mechanically sheared steel sheet [46].

Figure 14. Fractography images of the failed fatigue specimens highlighting the crack initiation from (a) the burr, and (b) the surface of the specimen [46].

Several models can be utilised to understand and qualify AHSS in terms of fatigue resistance. The S-N curve is commonly used to predict the fatigue life of materials, including AHSS, under constant stress amplitude loading. It provides a relationship between the stress amplitude (S) and the number of cycles to failure (N). AHSS materials typically show a higher fatigue strength due to their increased strength, but this also leads to reduced fatigue life under high cyclic stress. This behaviour changes in the negative direction to reduce the fatigue limit in the presence of defects. Figure 15 represents a typical S-N curve obtained from testing different AHSS specimens. A significant number of tests with different stress ratios should be applied and based on the number of cycles required to fail, the curve is obtained. A high fraction of high cycle fatigue investigations of AHSS employs the S-N curve with different parameters to find the fatigue resistance and fatigue limit of AHSS specimens. Materials may be subjected to both high-cycle (low-stress, many cycles) and low-cycle (high-stress, few cycles) fatigue loading. In high-cycle fatigue, the steel can withstand many cycles without failure, but its performance is influenced by microstructural features like grain size and phase distribution or defects. In low-cycle fatigue, the plastic deformation of the material is more pronounced, and the behaviour of the material exposed to high levels of strain is investigated [47-51].

Figure 15. The S-N curve obtained from fatigue tests performed on the AHSS specimens with different stress ratios [47].

For low-cycle fatigue, the strain-life approach is often used, which takes into account both elastic and plastic strain components. This model is particularly useful for predicting fatigue life under large deformation scenarios, such as those encountered in notches or stress concentrators studying the material's behaviour in a strain-controlled cyclic loading condition. Figure 16 shows a typical ε - N plot of AHSS specimens [52].

Figure 16. A typical ε - N plot of AHSS specimens comparing how different AHSS types react against applied cyclic strain [52].

In the high cycle regime, the staircase method is a fatigue testing technique used to determine a material's fatigue limit, typically employed when the fatigue limit is not well-defined. It involves subjecting specimens to cyclic loads at varying stress levels, increasing or decreasing the stress based on whether the previous specimen survives or fails. This creates a "staircase" pattern of stress levels, helping to estimate the material's fatigue limit with fewer specimens compared to other methods. The fatigue limit is calculated by averaging the failure and survival stresses. This method is particularly useful for statistical analysis in fatigue testing. Figure 17 represents different types of results obtained by the staircase method, employed to statistically estimate the fatigue limit of different AHSS specimens based on the Dixon-Mood method [53].

Figure 17. Staircase results for (a) AA 6082T6 and (b) DP1000. Dashed lines indicate the fatigue limit determined according to the Dixon-Mood method [53].

To further reduce the time, cost, and number of specimens for a fatigue study, rapid fatigue testing methods can be applied. These types of accelerated test methods, provide useful and valuable data regarding the fatigue limit and fatigue mechanisms of AHSS in a much faster, cheaper, and easier way.

Several methods for a reliable, accurate, and time- and cost-efficient fatigue limit evaluation have been proposed by many researchers in the last decades. The basis of most of these tests is to reduce the number of tests to obtain the fatigue limit in different materials by measuring a specific parameter during a load increase stepwise procedure and propose a method to relate the observed changes to the fatigue limit. Many of the researchers in the field of rapid fatigue evaluation, employ the concept of the self-heating phenomenon during cyclic loading to estimate the fatigue limit by measuring the surface temperature of the specimen using infrared (IR) cameras or thermocouples, and monitoring the changes in different stress levels. As shown in Figure 18, the temperature changes can be divided into three phases, a rapid increase at the beginning of the cyclic loading due to a higher heat generation than heat dissipation, a stabilisation stage (steady state) due to a balance between heat generation caused by the deformation and heat dissipation by forming microcracks, and ultimately a sudden rise near the fracture due to high plastic deformation and propagation of macrocrack [54].

Figure 18. Typical temperature evolution for a rapid low-cycle fatigue test [54].

The stiffness method in recent years was established to evaluate the fatigue limit of AHSS sheets by monitoring the changes in the stiffness and measuring the plastic strain values in the specimen during a stepwise cyclic load-increase test [55-58]. Figure 19 represents the schematic of the stiffness method and the typical data obtained from the test to be analysed in order to calculate the fatigue limit and the threshold stress.

Figure 19. Schematic representation of the stepwise loading test and inelastic strain range versus maximum stress to determine the fatigue limit [56].

The stiffness method measures fatigue damage by tracking the inelastic strain ($\Delta\varepsilon_p$) in a specimen after each fatigue block. $\Delta\varepsilon_p$ is then plotted against the maximum stress (σ_{max}) for each block. From this plot, the fatigue strength (σ_f) is determined by finding the point where the fitted line intersects the x-axis, which represents zero inelastic strain. This process is visually depicted in Figure 19, illustrating the relationship between stress and strain and helping identify material fatigue properties [56]. The method is straightforward and efficient, requiring neither specialised equipment nor complex data processing. This makes it an ideal optimisation tool for quickly evaluating the effects of various process conditions on fatigue behaviour [58].

Advanced simulation techniques, such as FEM (as the main simulation method) and crystal plasticity models, are used to predict fatigue behaviour by incorporating material defects, phase transformations, and microstructural evolution. These simulations help understand how defects affect crack initiation and propagation under various loading conditions, enabling better design and manufacturing practices. Simulating the fatigue process can be performed using different approaches. To mention examples of how simulation provides reliable and helpful information regarding fatigue, McDowell employed microstructure-sensitive fatigue modelling [59]. In their research, the authors explore the mechanisms of fatigue crack initiation and propagation in both low-cycle and high-cycle fatigue, considering the influence of notches of varying scales. They examine the relationship between remote loading conditions and cyclic plasticity/crack behaviour at the microstructural level, analysing how stress amplitude and material microstructure impact fatigue resistance. The study also assesses the material's intrinsic fatigue resistance, focusing on microplasticity percolation limits, and investigates the role of extrinsic factors, such as non-metallic inclusions, on fatigue performance. Figure 20 illustrates the accuracy of the simulation results for different inclusion aspect ratios compared to the values obtained experimentally.

Figure 20. Comparison of simulations for fatigue crack initiation life with experiments for completely reversed, strain-controlled loading as a function of inclusion aspect ratio [59].

Singh used the extended FEM (XFEM) method to study the fatigue life of a homogeneous plate containing multiple discontinuities (holes, minor cracks, and inclusions) with different characteristics by evaluating the stress intensity factors (SIFs). Results, as stated in Figure 21 prove how proper simulation approaches can be employed to investigate the negative effect of different defects on the fatigue properties [60].

Figure 21. Fatigue-life diagram for the centre crack with holes and minor cracks obtained by XFEM [60].

Phase transformation and volume fraction and its effect on the fatigue strength [61] and crack growth rates during cyclic loadings [55] are also highlighted fields to use simulation results in order to understand better the fatigue mechanisms.

3. Problem encountered and proposed approach

3.1 Description of the problem

Heavy-duty vehicles (HDVs), including lorries, buses, and coaches, are collectively responsible for more than 25% of the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions generated by road transport in the EU, accounting for over 6% of the total GHG emissions in the EU. Despite some improvements in fuel consumption efficiency in recent years, these emissions continue to rise, primarily due to the increasing volume of road freight traffic. In 2023, as part of its efforts to fight the climate crisis, the European Commission proposed a revision of Regulation 2019/1242, which established CO₂ emission standards for HDV. This revision will introduce stronger CO₂ emissions standards from 2030 onwards and extend the scope to include smaller trucks, city buses, long-distance buses, and trailers. The new targets aim to reduce CO₂ emissions per km from new HDVs by 90% by 2040, with intermediate goals for 2030 (-45%) and 2035 (-65%). Additionally, it limits the additional weight of alternatively fuelled or zero-emission vehicles to a maximum of 2 tonnes. Consequently, there is an urgent demand for new materials with enhanced mechanical properties to produce lighter, more efficient, and economically viable vehicles. HDVs can benefit from the lightweighting approach commonly applied to body-in-white (BiW) components of passenger cars and truck cabins, by replacing conventional steel alloys with AHSS. These AHSS solutions are recognised as the most cost-efficient means of achieving lightweighting, resulting in weight reductions ranging from 18 % to 35 % and cost savings from 3 € to 10 € per kg. HDV chassis components represent almost 35 % of the unladen weight of a rigid truck (12 tonnes gross vehicle weight) and have a significant potential for lightweighting, with the possibility of achieving weight reductions of at least 20 %. However, the thin AHSS (< 3 mm) used in BiW cannot be directly applied to HDV chassis systems (chassis frame, suspension system and wheels) nor the chassis of light-duty vehicles (LDV) or passenger cars. These components must withstand cyclic loads and require higher thicknesses (> 3 mm), factors not considered in AHSSs for BiW. Therefore, this scenario presents a wide range of opportunities for the development of new, thicker high-strength steel grades tailored for fatigue applications showing improved combinations of strength, fatigue resistance and ductility, thereby contributing significantly to further weight reduction and overall enhanced performance.

This applies to thick 1st Generation AHSSs, including complex phase (CP) and dual-phase (DP) steels, as well as spring steels. The 1st Gen of thin AHSSs is known for its high strength (UTS > 900 MPa), and relatively high ductility (>13% elongation). These characteristics enable the production of high-performance components with thinner gauges and more complex geometries. These attributes, when replicated in thick 1st Gen AHSS steels, render them especially suitable for use in structural chassis systems, such as crossbeam members of chassis trucks, wheels, and suspension arms. Currently, these components are primarily based on mild steels or, at best, high-strength low-alloy steels (HSLA). Similarly, the higher quality of spring steels made from 100% recycled material (scrap), achieved through enhanced cleanliness due to better scrap quality, plays a crucial role in producing lighter components, like leaf springs for suspension systems. Given the limited research on thick AHSS and the impact of scrap quality on spring steels, it is essential to gain a comprehensive understanding of how scrap quality and microstructure affect various mechanical properties, including fatigue, fracture, and fatigue notch sensitivity, before their safe and widespread implementation in the automotive chassis industry, which had a market size of USD 64 billion in 2022.

3.2 Steel4Fatigue approach

Steel4Fatigue main objective is to establish a knowledge foundation for thick 1st Gen AHSS and spring steels, to promote their extensive adoption in the automotive chassis industry. The project is dedicated to enhancing the understanding of the relationship between microstructure and mechanical performance in AHSS and spring steels. It seeks to demonstrate the potential of these steels in the production of lightweight automotive parts, to achieve a remarkable 20% reduction in weight compared to current steel solutions, all while maintaining affordability. To do that, a thorough microstructural and mechanical characterisation campaign will be carried out on 9 different steel grades including thick sheets and rod steels (Table 1)

The project also includes the development of time- and cost-efficient characterisation methodologies and predictive microstructural models. These tools will contribute to accelerating the design and optimisation of new high-strength steels and steelmaking processes, ultimately reducing time-to-market for high-performance steel products.

Finally, the viability of the new steel solutions to manufacture lightweight chassis automotive components will be assessed in semi-industrial trials. The results of *Steel4Fatigue* will help to consolidate the role of steel as a cost-efficient and sustainable lightweight solution for future mobility.

More details about the holistic methodology implemented in *Steel4Fatigue* to attain the proposed objectives are given in Section 6.

Table 1. Steel grades investigated in *Steel4Fatigue*.

Material designation	Steel supplier	Thickness (mm)
S500MC	SSAB	8
S500MC Plus		8
HR550		8
700MC PLUS		8
800CP		8
1000CP		8
HRCP800SF	AMMR	3
HRDP780		3
62SiCr7	SIDENOR	Ø 20

4. *Steel4Fatigue* objectives and expected outcomes

As mentioned before, *Steel4Fatigue* aims to stimulate the development of new advanced high-performance steel products with enhanced mechanical properties and promote their widespread deployment in the automotive sector, contributing to more sustainable mobility. To achieve that, the following 8 key technical objectives (TO) are defined:

- **TO#1. To understand the relationship between microstructure and mechanical properties of thick 1st Gen AHSS.** The relationship between microstructural characteristics and mechanical properties of different thick 1st Gen AHSS steels will be carefully assessed through advanced microstructural and mechanical characterisation techniques.
- **TO#2. To understand the relationship between scrap quality and mechanical properties of spring steels.** The relationship between scrap quality, microstructural characteristics (inclusions, internal and surface defects), and mechanical properties of different spring steels made from 100% recycled steel will be carefully assessed through advanced mechanical characterisation techniques.
- **TO#3. To gain knowledge on some of the most critical in-use properties of thick AHSS and spring steels for automotive.** The project will address relevant properties like fracture toughness and fatigue, which are deemed critical for a safe implementation in the automobile.
- **TO#4. To establish time- and cost-efficient characterisation methods for rapid market uptake of new steel products.** The project will provide affordable rapid and simpler testing methodologies to estimate the fatigue performance of thick AHSS and long steel products. This will help to assist new material design and make decisions at the early stages of development, reducing the time to market of new steel products.
- **TO#5. To develop advanced finite element models for sheared edge shape (manufacturing processes) and fatigue prediction.** A novel modelling approach for edge shearing and fatigue performance taking the intrinsic material property into account, shall be developed and verified.
- **TO#6. To develop digital microstructural models for mechanical performance prediction.** Microstructure-sensitive models for thick 1st Gen AHSS will be developed, bridging the microstructure characterisation with the in-service properties. This will provide in-depth and quantitative knowledge in understanding the structure-property relation of these steels and advanced models and digital tools to describe these steels and predict their properties.
- **TO#7. To demonstrate the industrial viability of the proposed steel solutions for the production of chassis components.** The feasibility of implementing the proposed solutions in high-volume production with current technologies will be analysed. Different structural components will be manufactured, and fatigue tested.
- **TO#8. To quantify the environmental impact of the proposed solutions.** Environmental results will be analysed in terms of their compliance with the DNSH (Do no significant harm) principle. The environmental benefits and drawbacks compared to current steel solutions and other competitive materials will be assessed.

The expected outcomes (EO) are the following:

- **EO#1: New high-strength steel products with enhanced fatigue resistance.** The *Steel4Fatigue* project aims to advance scientific and technological knowledge for developing new AHSSs and recycled spring steels with improved cleanliness and fatigue properties. These innovations will benefit industrial applications, particularly in the automotive sector, by enabling weight reduction and enhanced performance. The project will explore the relationship between microstructure, mechanical performance, and scrap quality, providing guidelines for steel manufacturers to optimize materials. Extensive data on fatigue resistance, fracture toughness, and formability for thick AHSSs will drive research and development, creating a reference framework that fosters innovation and sustainability in the steel industry.
- **EO#2: More efficient testing and modelling methods to predict in-use properties of high-strength steels.** The *Steel4Fatigue* project aims to deliver substantial benefits to the automotive and steel industries by introducing innovative tools for manufacturing and fatigue evaluation of thick AHSS and long steel products. Key advantages include: 1) reducing time-to-market and costs for new high-performance steel products, 2) minimizing production failures and prototyping errors through accurate material parameter determination and improved simulation models, and 3) decreasing material waste by replacing trial-and-error methods with digital predictive models. These advancements promise cost-efficiency, sustainability, and enhanced product development.
- **EO#3: Lighter, durable, and more sustainable vehicle structures.** As outlined in the European Green Deal, the transport sector plays a crucial role in achieving the goal of making the EU the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. This requires a fundamental shift towards zero-emission mobility and a commitment to sustainability across all transport vehicles. The innovative high-strength steel solutions proposed in *Steel4Fatigue* align with these objectives by enabling weight reduction (targeting 20%) in automotive structural components while meeting durability and performance requirements related to stiffness, twisting, and fatigue. The lightweight potential of the proposed steels is achieved thanks to their high fatigue strength level (>300 MPa), lower notch sensitivity, higher material cleanliness, and enhanced formability, which enables component downgauging and forming more complex geometries. These advancements lead to more efficient vehicle structures with an improved performance-to-weight ratio, contributing to weight reduction. Importantly, weight reduction directly correlates with a reduction in GHG emissions. It is estimated that a 100 kg reduction in HDV weight can result in a lifetime saving of 2 tonnes of greenhouse gases over the vehicle's total life cycle. For BEVs and zero-emission vehicles (ZEVs), which rely on heavy battery packs (2-3 tonnes for electric HDV), reducing the total vehicle mass is crucial. This not only improves battery efficiency but also enhances freight transport efficiency by increasing payload. Furthermore, as these battery packs need protection in the event of a crash, the development of advanced steels that can fulfil these requirements is paramount. In this context, thick 1st Gen AHSS with a balance of strength and ductility such as CP and DP-like steels, will be crucial to reduce the weight of the chassis frame and wheels, which collectively account for 18% of the unladen weight of a rigid truck (12 tonnes gross vehicle weight). Similarly, higher-quality spring steels made entirely from recycled steel, representing another 18% of the unladen truck's weight, offer opportunities for additional chassis weight reduction and improved fatigue performance.

5. Innovative aspects of *Steel4Fatigue*: Progress beyond the SoA

Steel4Fatigue will go one step beyond the State of the Art in the characterisation and modelling of thick 1st Gen AHSS steels for automotive applications. The main innovations of the project are described below.

1. **Fatigue:** *Steel4Fatigue* will advance the understanding of how microstructure influences the fatigue resistance of thick 1st Gen AHSS and how scrap quality influences the fatigue resistance of spring steels. Furthermore, rapid test methods for estimating fatigue life will be used (explained in the methodology section). These approaches offer a substantial reduction in both time and costs when evaluating fatigue resistance. They can serve as efficient screening methods for designing and selecting materials with enhanced fatigue properties.
2. **Fracture toughness:** In *Steel4Fatigue*, further investigations will be conducted to enhance understanding of the fracture mechanisms occurring during the fatigue process in thick 1st Gen AHSSs and spring steels. The project will delve into the intricacies of fatigue crack initiation and propagation, providing valuable insights into how microstructure and fracture mechanisms influence fatigue behaviour and can be used to predict relevant parameters, such as fatigue notch sensitivity. Additionally, a novel rapid procedure for estimating the fracture toughness of thick 1st Gen AHSS and spring steels will be implemented.
3. **Microstructural modelling of AHSS:** In *Steel4Fatigue*, high-resolution digital microstructural models with crystal plasticity and damage models will be developed to accurately represent the intricate microstructures of complex phases and new-generation steels. These models will enable integrated damage-fatigue assessments of these advanced steels, providing a comprehensive knowledge and data repository for further optimisation of these materials in a holistic overview of mechanical properties.
4. **Material defects and fatigue modelling:** In *Steel4Fatigue*, a fracture-based modelling approach will be developed to predict features introduced during cold-forming processes, mainly damage, including deformation of already existing defects, and residual stresses. This model will be coupled to an FE model for predicting fatigue damage of thick AHSSs, incorporating insights from microstructural modelling. The fracture criterion for cut edge prediction introduced in *Fatigue4Light* project will be further explored here for other forming processes and larger sheet thicknesses.

6. *Steel4Fatigue* strategy to reach the objectives

As the proposal outlines, a systematic and multi-disciplinary methodology will be implemented in *Steel4Fatigue* to reach the project objectives. The methodology can be divided into 4 distinct phases or stages (Figure 22): 1) Materials for fatigue applications, 2) Characterisation of in-use properties, 3) Modelling and simulation and 4) Industrial implementation. The following paragraphs describe the most important methods within each phase and explain how they will be applied to address the abovementioned topics.

Figure 22. Overview of the methodology implemented to reach the objectives of Steel4Fatigue.

6.1 Phase 1. Materials for fatigue applications

The project will start with the definition of the most promising materials for chassis systems (chassis frame, suspension system and wheels), targeting a weight reduction of the part of at least 20% compared to reference materials. The selection of the 1st Gen AHSSs for chassis applications will be drawn from the knowledge acquired by the partners in previous projects, such as *Fatigue4Light* [62], combined with the expertise within the consortium. Moreover, the project will investigate the impact of scrap quality on spring steel cleanliness and its influence on fatigue resistance. This will involve adjusting steelmaking conditions to develop new spring steels that exhibit improved fatigue properties while incorporating a higher percentage of high-quality scrap. These challenges will be addressed through the following material investigations.

6.1.1 Thick advanced high-strength steels (AHSSs)

Truck chassis frames (Figure 33b), which account for 18% of the unladen weight, have traditionally relied on mild and HSLA steel, with S500MC being a common choice (Figure 23a). Previous projects like *Warmlight* [63] and *Worthtruck* [64] have explored more advanced materials, including warm and hot-forming steels, which can reach strengths of up to 1000 MPa. Nevertheless, the considerable energy costs associated with part production at elevated temperatures, along with the high-notch sensitivity of these materials, have posed challenges for their widespread adoption. This is particularly crucial for truck chassis frames, which must deal with defects that can compromise their fatigue resistance [46]. Considering these challenges, the project will focus on new thick (around 8 mm thickness) hot rolled (HR) 1st Gen AHSSs with complex microstructures (Table 1) based on ferrite-bainite matrix with martensite and austenite islands, which has demonstrated high toughness in thin plates [65]. These efforts will highlight the potential for lightweight solutions using cold-forming materials with reasonable production costs. Material selection will be based on the approach proposed by Parareda et al. [45], which relates fracture toughness measurements to the fatigue resistance of the chosen materials (Figure 23b) obtained in Phase 2. The materials exhibiting higher fatigue resistance (σ_f) and fracture toughness will be selected because they are expected to demonstrate superior fatigue behaviour, even in the presence of defects, resulting in a lower fatigue strength reduction factor (k_f). In other words, they will possess greater damage tolerance.

Figure 23. a) Banana curve for AHSS and b) fatigue and fracture toughness graph, in both highlighting the Steel4Fatigue solutions in blue (thick CP and DP-like steels).

On the other hand, thick AHSS for fatigue applications must possess superior formability. Formability is crucial to achieving complex geometries, resulting in lighter components. Apart from truck chassis frames, a prominent example of this need for formability is in the manufacturing of wheels for BEVs. The prevalent materials for mass-market wheel construction are cold-formed steel and cast aluminium. Although forged aluminium, magnesium, and Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) are used in premium sports cars, they remain prohibitively expensive for mass-market applications. When considering the choice between stamped steel and cast aluminium, steel wheels emerge as a cost-effective, sustainable, and often lighter solution, especially when casted wheels are not optimised. DP600 is the primary material for the aesthetic disc of steel wheels, ensuring acceptable fatigue performance after extensive forming processes. A new hybrid steel-aluminium wheel has recently been developed by MW as an alternative to casted aluminium wheels. This solution is 20% lighter, significantly cheaper, and has a lower CO₂ footprint than a full aluminium product (60% less) [66]. This is primarily because a significant part of the hybrid wheel (the disc) is made of steel (Figure 33a), which has a lower CO₂ footprint per kg than aluminium. The adoption of this new hybrid product could be hindered by the aesthetic appeal of the casted wheel, which is difficult to replicate through steel stamping using current steel grades. However, the aerodynamic features of these new wheels for EVs can bridge this gap. The best aerodynamic wheels are mainly flat, and a focus on steel disc formability is crucial to bringing this product to the mass market. This would result in weight reduction, cost reduction, and CO₂ reduction for wheels, all while maintaining the aesthetic appeal that customers desire. In the context of *Steel4Fatigue*, new CP and DP-like steels, namely HRCP800SF and HRDP780 below 4 mm thickness, will be proposed for wheel applications. These steels are expected to strike an excellent balance between formability and fatigue resistance, both evaluated in Phase 2. Additionally, the project will explore a new complex phase grade with retained austenite. The inclusion of retained austenite is anticipated to provide enhanced formability to these materials, akin to the 3rd generation AHSS grades [67].

6.1.2 High-strength steel in long format

The increasing demand for reduced environmental impact in the steelmaking process, coupled with the rising requirements for engineering components like leaf springs in heavier BEVs such as trucks, necessitates the exploration of innovative production methods to enhance the mechanical properties of these steels. Spring steels can achieve

high strength (UTS > 2000 MPa) through various approaches, including high silicon content to boost yield strength, cold deformation for deformation hardening, and microalloying for precipitation hardening. Silicon plays a critical role in influencing cementite precipitation during tempering, shifting the embrittlement range to higher temperatures. This enables tempering at lower temperatures, achieving high strength without compromising the microstructure. However, silicon is a potent deoxidiser and readily reacts with oxygen, potentially causing undesirable decarburisation when the steel is exposed to high temperatures for extended periods. This issue has been addressed through induction hardening, which significantly reduces treatment times, rendering decarburisation negligible. Reducing treatment and processing times also presents an opportunity to leverage microalloying for precipitation hardening. It allows for the prevention or delay of austenite recrystallization, resulting in highly deformed austenite and a fine grain structure in the final product. Although various alloying strategies involving elements like high Ni, Mo, Ti, B, and rare earth metals have been employed in spring steels to enhance tensile strength, improve toughness, or enhance corrosion resistance, their practical application remains limited. Industrial practices predominantly revolve around SiCr and SiCrV steels.

However, just as surface defects can impact the fatigue performance of chassis parts, internal defects related to material cleanliness can undermine efforts to enhance the in-service fatigue performance of spring steels. This is primarily due to the high fatigue notch sensitivity of these materials, a characteristic that generally increases with their strength, as depicted in Figure 24. In applications like leaf springs, where bending stresses are prevalent, the surface and subsurface regions are of particular concern regarding issues such as microinclusions, segregations, decarburization, and more. Within the *Steel4Fatigue*, a standard spring steel grade (62SiCr7) will be selected and produced through both the conventional process using 100% recycled material (scrap) and a new optimised process that incorporates a higher proportion of high-quality scrap. This will enable a comparison of the resulting material cleanliness and its impact on fatigue performance.

Figure 24. Relationship between fatigue limit and defect size, according to Kitagawa.

The investigated spring steel production process comprises an electric arc furnace, ladle furnace, continuous casting, and hot rolling. This steel grade will be manufactured through both the standard process and a process optimised with specific parameters, such as ladle gas stirring, temperatures and casting speed among others. This

optimisation will be carried out throughout different steps of the steelmaking process: secondary metallurgy, which includes all the ladle operations (degassing, alloy addition, inclusion removal, inclusion chemistry modification, homogenisation, etc.) and continuous casting. To this purpose, among other tasks, internal meetings will be organised with the main departments of the productive area of SIDENOR: quality, melt shop, process and product engineering, continuous casting, etc.

Given the ability to modify multiple variables within the steelmaking process to fine-tune the mechanical properties and quality of the final product, the rapid testing methods developed in Phase 2 will serve as invaluable tools in the development of steel products designed for optimal fatigue resistance.

6.2 Phase 2. Characterisation of in-use properties

The project's second phase aims to characterise some of the most critical in-use properties of high-strength steels for automotive applications through mechanical tests. This phase will focus on the following research topics.

6.2.1 Microstructural characterisation

The microstructure plays a pivotal role in the fatigue performance of the selected steels in Phase 1. Consequently, a comprehensive microstructural characterisation aimed at identifying and quantifying the microstructural constituents of the investigated steels will be conducted. A combination of fundamental and advanced microstructural characterisation techniques will be employed. These techniques include Light Optical Microscopy (LOM), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), High-Resolution Electron Backscattered Diffraction (HR-EBSD), and nanoindentation measurements [68]. LOM investigations will provide initial insights into the primary microstructural constituents and the distribution of secondary phases within the matrix. High-magnification SEM measurements will allow for a more detailed description of the morphology and size of individual phases. EBSD analysis will be used to develop the microstructural model described in Phase 3 and to quantify microstructural damage, in conjunction with nanoindentation data [69].

6.2.2 Fatigue

The effect of material properties on fatigue behaviour depends on the fracture mechanisms. In materials with defects, either internal or external, fatigue life can be reduced because such defects act as nucleated microcracks. Therefore, fatigue life is primarily governed by crack propagation, and materials with high toughness or crack propagation resistance (typically associated with lower yield strength - σ_{YS}) exhibit higher fatigue resistance. Conversely, in defect-free materials without internal or external irregularities, fatigue life is primarily governed by crack nucleation. Both situations will be addressed in *Steel4Fatigue* by testing polished specimens (defect-free) and specimens with defects introduced through processes like edge shearing, bending, and steelmaking (inclusions). This approach will allow to assess the fatigue notch sensitivity of the investigated materials. Since chassis components are designed for high cycle fatigue conditions (from 100k to 2M cycles), the steels investigated in *Steel4Fatigue* will be characterised using S-N curves (ISO 1099) [70]. All tests will be conducted at a stress ratio (R) of -1 (tension-compression) using hourglass specimens for the polished

condition (Figure 25). Additionally, specific specimen geometries, such as punched open-hole (Figure 25) and bent specimens (Figure 30), will be used to evaluate the impact of defects on fatigue performance. Furthermore, the fatigue fracture surfaces of the tested samples will be carefully examined using the stereomicroscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM), while the surface of the punched edge will be analysed by 3D profilometry to get the critical defect (roughness value, R_v) [71] as well as the edge profile.

Figure 25. Punched open-hole and hourglass fatigue specimen geometries. Dimensions expressed in mm.

To rapidly assess the fatigue resistance of the different materials and understand the mechanisms operating during each stage of fatigue, *Steel4Fatigue* will employ two rapid fatigue testing methods: the *stiffness method* and the *self-heating method*. It should be noted that these methods aim to provide an initial fatigue assessment for material selection and to evaluate various fatigue conditions. However, they should not be used for design purposes.

Eurecat developed the *stiffness method* in the *FormPlanet* project (patent EP20382742). The tests will be carried out following the recommendations of the CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) 18107-2 [72]. The method relies on the study of the fatigue damage evolution of a specimen developed during cyclic testing. Through monitoring such damage, the method allows to determine the different stages of fatigue crack growth and estimate the fatigue properties of the material either related to damage mechanics (fatigue limit) or fracture mechanics (crack propagation) in a short time (hours instead of months using the conventional S-N curves) and with a reduced number of specimens, usually 3 [73]. Under cyclic loading at a given stress amplitude, the incipient fatigue damage evolves from micro to macrocracks (6000 cycles at 30 Hz are sufficient in metallic materials). This damage evolution measured using conventional extensometers or Digital Image Correlation (DIC) systems, in terms of plastic strain is determined for the stress amplitude of the tests. It is denoted $\Delta\varepsilon_p$. The maximum $\Delta\varepsilon_p$ for a given load can be determined for each series according to Figure 26b. A curve representing $\Delta\varepsilon_p$ evolution relating to the stress amplitude (σ_a) can be plotted (Figure 26c). Linear regression is done using the points that describe microcrack propagation, and the intersection between this straight line and the abscissa axis can be considered as the mean fatigue limit (σ_f) at 2 million cycles (Figure 26d). The methodology has been validated in several AHSSs and will be applied in *Steel4Fatigue* to determine the fatigue strength of selected thick AHSS steels [53]. Furthermore, the methodology will be enhanced to provide rapid predictions for not only the fatigue limit but also the complete S-N curve [74]. The same

fatigue specimen geometries as the S-N curve (hourglass, open-hole, and bent) will be used to determine the fatigue resistance. The results will be compared to standard S-N curves.

Figure 26. a) Strain monitoring in the rapid fatigue test based on damage evolution, b) successive series of cyclic loads with increasing stress amplitude and strain measurements at $\sigma_{YS}/2$, c) strain evolution throughout the test and d) evaluation of the fatigue limit.

The *self-heating method* using thermocouples is widely used at AMMR [75]. The tests will be carried out following the recommendations of the CWA 18107-1 [76]. The method relies on the evolution of the temperature of a specimen under cyclic loading. This temperature elevation is caused by the microplasticity at the origin of fatigue phenomena. This method will be used to predict the fatigue properties through this temperature evolution in a minimal time (several hours in comparison with almost one month with conventional fatigue tests). Under cyclic loading at a given stress amplitude, the temperature θ generally reaches a stabilised value (6000 cycles at 30 Hz are sufficient in metallic materials), as shown in Figure 27a. This steady-state temperature is determined for the stress amplitude of the tests. It is denoted $\bar{\theta}$. Then, there is a return at thermal equilibrium without any loading during an equivalent time to the one for the cyclic loading. The mean steady-state temperature elevation for each series can be determined according to Figure 27b. A self-heating curve representing the mean steady-state temperature elevation relating to the stress amplitude can be plotted (Figure 27c). Linear regression is done on the last points of the self-heating curve, and the intersection between this straight line and the abscissa axis can be considered the mean endurance limit at 2 million cycles. In this case, the focus will be on determining the fatigue resistance of the parent material. The specimen geometry will consist of a strip measuring 120 x 10 mm.

Figure 27. a) Temperature monitoring in the rapid fatigue test based on self-heating, b) successive series of cyclic loads with increasing stress amplitude and c) temperature evolution throughout the test and evaluation of the fatigue limit.

Both rapid fatigue testing methods rely on quantifying damage evolution, either through strain or temperature measurements. Therefore, the rapid fatigue tests will be paused at different damage levels to investigate fatigue damage evolution within the selected AHSSs as illustrated in Figure 28a. Subsequently, these test specimens will undergo SEM analysis to examine the presence of fatigue microcracks and their interactions with the microstructure Figure 28b. The analysis will be coupled with EBSD and nanoindentation maps to clearly identify the fatigue mechanism at the microstructural level. The knowledge derived from these observations will be instrumental in refining the fatigue model in Phase 3, enabling a more precise representation of fatigue behaviour.

Figure 28. a) Different stages of fatigue damage analysis related to microcrack propagation from a defect. b) Fatigue crack propagation through the microstructure of S500MC grade.

6.2.3 Fracture toughness

Fracture toughness is a critical material property for understanding the cracking resistance of AHSS. Therefore, evaluating the fracture toughness properties of AHSS sheets has become of paramount importance to steel manufacturers and parts manufacturers. The fracture toughness of the steel grades investigated in *Steel4Fatigue* will be assessed using the Essential Work of Fracture (EWF) methodology [77], which has emerged as an alternative to standard fracture mechanics procedures (ASTM E1820, ASTM E2472) [78]. This method has been employed in various research works to characterise the crack propagation resistance of AHSS and to comprehend their fatigue notch sensitivity [79]. Consequently, it has become a valuable tool for assessing damage tolerance and is particularly useful for examining the influence of microstructure on fracture behaviour [80]. In this project, EWF tests will be conducted following the guidelines of the CEN Workshop Agreement CWA 17793:2021 [81]. Rectangular Double Edge Notched Tension (DENT) specimens measuring 200 x 55 mm will be used for materials close to 3 mm in thickness (Figure 29). Conversely, Single Edge Notched Bending (SENB) specimens measuring 120 x 30 mm will be employed for thicker materials to reduce testing loads. To mitigate the influence of notch radius on EWF results, fatigue pre-cracks will be initiated at the notch root. In EWF tests, up to 15 DENT or SENB specimens with varying ligament lengths (l_0) are tested until fracture at a constant crosshead displacement rate, and the load and load-line displacement are recorded during the tests. The specific total work of fracture (w_f) for each specimen is determined by integrating the energy under the load vs. load-line displacement curve and dividing it by the initial cross-sectional area (Figure 29b). The specific essential work of fracture (w_e) is then determined through linear extrapolation of w_f vs. l_0 data to ligament

zero (Figure 29c). The slope of this linear regression represents the non-essential plastic work (w_p) multiplied by a geometry factor (β).

Figure 29. a) DENT geometry used for EWF tests. b) Typical load-displacement curves obtained from EWF tests. c) Schematic representation of the w_f vs. l_0 plot and determination of the specific essential work for fracture (w_e) and the fracture toughness at crack initiation (w_e^i).

The fracture toughness at crack initiation (w_e^i) is calculated as an average of specific work of fracture initiation (w_f^i) values for different ligament lengths. These w_f^i values are derived from the area under load-displacement curves up to the point of crack growth initiation (Figure 29b). To determine the moment of crack growth initiation, a high-resolution video camera synchronized with the testing machine will be used.

Furthermore, the project will explore the use of a new Cracking Resistance Index (CR_I) to classify the crack propagation resistance of the selected steel grades, particularly for thick materials. The CR_I is calculated as follows:

$$CR_I [\%] = \frac{W_{fL8}}{UTS \cdot TE \cdot t_0 \cdot l_0^2} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_{fL8} is the energy under the load-displacement curve of a DENT specimen with a ligament length of 8 mm, UTS represents the ultimate tensile strength, TE denotes the total elongation, t_0 signifies the sheet thickness, and l_0 refers to the ligament length. The combination of rapid fatigue tests and the CR_I might be used as a fast and cost-effective method to estimate the fatigue notch sensitivity of AHSS. This methodology could be easily implemented as a routine procedure for in-plant quality control, material selection, and acceptance. It will be validated in thick AHSS for the first time in *Steel4Fatigue*.

6.2.4 Formability of thick AHSS

Formability is a critical property for AHSS, especially in cold-forming operations, as it determines whether a part can be successfully manufactured. Global formability refers to the resistance of the material against the formation of localised necking in deformation processes where relatively large regions of material are deformed simultaneously, such as stretch forming, drawing, etc. This property is typically assessed using the FLC. The FLC defines the deformation limits of a material for various strain paths, represented by different combinations of major (ϵ_1) and minor (ϵ_2) strains in the Forming Limit Diagram (FLD) depicted in Figure 30b. Strain points below the FLC represent the safe zone, where sheet metal can be formed without the risk of localised necking, while points above the FLC indicate a risk of failure. It is important to note that the experimental determination of the FLC is typically limited to materials with a maximum thickness of 4 mm. Therefore, only the global formability of the selected steels for wheels, HRCP800SF and HRDP780, will be assessed according to ISO 12004 [83] using a Nakajima tool (Figure 30a). The results from these formability tests will be used as input for the design of the wheel to be manufactured in Phase 4.

To assess the impact of forming on fatigue resistance, a specific fatigue test will complement the formability test. This fatigue test, similar to those reported in the literature [84], will involve the use of a bent specimen measuring 150 x 20 mm, as shown in Figure 30c. This bent specimen will be manufactured for all the selected steels intended for wheels and subjected to cyclic loading at R of -1, following the conventional S-N curve and rapid testing methods. The unique geometry of these specimens will enable the evaluation of the effect of pre-strain and residual stresses induced during the cold-forming process. This information, when combined with the FLC, will be crucial for understanding how cold forming affects the microstructure and fatigue performance of AHSSs. The main advantage of these tests is that they are not limited by material thickness, allowing all the materials from the *Steel4Fatigue* project to be tested using this approach. This comprehensive testing will facilitate the modelling of the forming effect on the final components in Phase 3 of the project.

Figure 30. a) Geometry of the Nakajima tool used for FLC determination according to ISO 12004, b) schematic representation of an FLC and c) Bent specimen geometry to consider the forming effects on the fatigue resistance.

6.3 Phase 3. Modelling and simulation

The third phase of the project aims to develop new modelling solutions to predict the fatigue resistance of AHSS, taking into account microstructural and part manufacturing features. This phase will focus on the following research topics.

6.3.1 Microstructure modelling for scale bridging from micro to macro scale

A new micromechanical model will be developed in *Steel4Fatigue* for better prediction of damage initiation, which is crucial to improving the material microstructure [85]. Micromechanical modelling of AHSS microstructures is used as the main virtual tool for analysing the effects of various microstructural features, e.g. grain boundaries, crystal lattice, and volume fraction, on macroscopic mechanical fatigue behaviour (Figure 31).

Figure 31. Micromechanical modelling of the virtual AHSS microstructure based on EBSD. CPM is used to predict the mechanical fatigue response.

In this modelling approach, the grain morphology is based on an artificially generated, simplified virtual microstructure (representative volume element), using the results of an experimental microstructure characterisation, e.g. EBSD, as input. The mechanical behaviour is modelled with the crystal plasticity approach implemented into a FEM framework. The crystal plasticity theory assumes that plastic deformation occurs by dislocation glides in crystallographic slip planes. Crystal plasticity modelling offers a much more physically oriented description of mechanical behaviour than the classical continuum mechanical description of plasticity. Combining micromechanical modelling and an advanced physics-based description of plasticity provides the possibility to consider AHSS microstructures that are either single- or multi-phase (e.g. DP steels) and have a face-centred cubic (FCC) or body-centred cubic (BCC) crystal structure. To overcome the scientific challenge of identifying a unique set of crystal plasticity parameters for each phase (e.g. critical resolved shear stress or elastic constants), extensive comparison with different experimental mechanical tests under static or cyclic loading will be performed. Another scientific challenge lies in the representation of the complex partially hierarchical microstructure. Since not all the fine-scaled microstructural features can be resolved in the model due to the high computational effort, reasonable assumptions/simplifications are made for this. In general, emphasis is placed on achieving a good compromise between accuracy and computational effort, which is particularly important when considering fatigue processes due to the naturally large time scale. The results obtained in the model will be compared to the experimental results, especially with the ones from the paused rapid fatigue tests and punching operations, where damage is already developed as described in Phase 2.

The new fatigue modelling approaches are expected to achieve 5% additional weight savings thanks to the best material selection and development for fatigue applications.

6.3.2 Material defects and fatigue modelling

The predictions of material damage from the different manufacturing processes like shear and forming are crucial for the fatigue life prediction of components under cyclic loads [86, 87]. In *Steel4Fatigue* a model based on the developments achieved in the *Fatigue4Light* [62] project will be used and further developed. Such model addresses one of the main challenges in process modelling, consisting of numerically being able to treat the extremely large deformation occurring in the shearing processes. Large deformation in ductile material fracture demands discretisation methods that are efficient and stable but also possible to combine with other methods e.g. particle-based methods that can be combined with element-based methods. The method will be developed for thick AHSS where the residual stresses and surface morphology are critical for chassis

applications. The results will be validated by measuring the surface shape and parameters using a 3D optical profilometer.

The manufacturing simulations will be performed in commercial finite element software (LS-Dyna) to enhance industrial usability. The simulations will utilise a plasticity model valid for high local strains that are calibrated using inverse modelling of standard tensile tests. Furthermore, a ductile damage criterion will be used to predict damage, and in the case of shear cutting, failure where the model parameters are determined from one punching experiment on each steel grade together with the tensile tests. These simulations will provide the actual final geometry of the formed part (Figure 32a) as well as residual stresses (Figure 32b) and plastic deformations (Figure 32c). The latter feature results in a hardness increase and will also be utilised in a novel approach to ovalize already existing defects in the steel increasing their harmfulness for the fatigue strength. This model is then used in Phase 4 to predict the fatigue strength and life of the demonstrators to validate the approach (Figure 32d). Finally, the modelling is used for optimising the design and manufacturing of the demonstrators highlighting potential weight reductions using the results from *Steel4Fatigue*.

Figure 32. Modelling of the sheared edge a) morphology and b) residual stresses for thin AHSS. c) Modelling of the forming process and d) fatigue resistance. [87]

6.4 Phase 4. Industrial implementation

The last phase of the project addresses the industrial implementation of thick AHSS steels for manufacturing automotive chassis components. To validate the process viability and guarantee the success of their manufacturability, first, a complete forming analysis will be performed using the material cards and simulation models generated in the project. The simulations will be carried out using commercial FE-software (Abaqus, LS-Dyna) and will help to identify critical areas and hot spots (Figure 32d). Furthermore, the new microstructural and fatigue criteria developed in *Steel4Fatigue* will be implemented as post-processing routines in the commercial software for industrial usability.

Two scenarios will be considered (Figure 33): a) the manufacturing of a prototype truck crossbeam member using existing dies and part geometry and b) the manufacturing of a new disc wheel using new dies and geometry. The latter scenario will require the development of a prototype stamping die and the design of the forming process to meet the formability requirements of the new materials. The design of the new wheel will aim to achieve an optimal balance between performance and weight, taking advantage of the superior formability and fatigue properties of the new AHSS. The robustness of the process will be carefully assessed, with a special focus on predicting part quality and addressing geometrical deviations, which are critical factors in industrial production.

After virtual validation and once the forming parameters are defined, semi-industrial stamping trials will be conducted by SCANIA and MW in their respective stamping plants

(Figure 33c). The parts produced in these trials will then undergo fatigue testing, with SCANIA testing the crossbeam member and MW testing the wheel, to validate the fatigue predictions and confirm the achieved weight reduction. This weight reduction will also be used to verify the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) analysis conducted in the project.

Finally, the results, knowledge, and strategies employed to upgrade these demonstrators will serve as examples in the guidelines for fatigue-dimensioned components. This aims to benefit other applications by sharing the developments achieved in the *Steel4Fatigue* project.

Figure 33. Demonstrators that will be produced in the *Steel4Fatigue* are a) wheel for cars and b) cross member for heavy-duty vehicles. c) stamping press for semi-industrial trials of crossbeam members.

7. References

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